

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE WORKS OF GREAT THINKER SCIENTISTS IN DEVELOPING TOLERANCE THINKING IN FUTURE SOCIAL WORKERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14906001>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the moral issues and tolerance of the peoples of Central Asia in the works of encyclopedists Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, Ibn Sina and Abu Raykhan Al-Biruni.

Keywords: education, tolerance, people, scientist, work, country, tolerance, value, morality, culture, social life.

BO'LAJAK IJTIMOYIY ISH XODIMLARIDA TOLERANTLIK TAFAKKURINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA BUYUK MUTAFAKKIR ALLOMALAR ASARLARINING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada qomusiy olimlardan Abu Nasr Farobiy, Ibn Sino va Abu Rayhon Beruniy asarlarida Markaziy Osiyo xalqlarining axloqiy masalalar va tolerantlik haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, tolerantlik, xalq, olim, asar, mamlakat, tolerantlik, qadriyat, axloq, madaniyat, ijtimoiy hayot.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ТРУДОВ ВЕЛИКИХ МЫСЛИТЕЛЕЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ТОЛЕРАНТНОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ У БУДУЩИХ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ РАБОТНИКОВ

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Аннотация: В статье дается подробная информация о нравственных проблемах и толерантности народов Средней Азии в трудах энциклопедистов Абу Насра аль-Фараби, Ибн Сины и Абу Райхана аль-Бируни.

Ключевые слова: образование, толерантность, люди, ученый, труд, страна, толерантность, ценности, этика, культура, общественная жизнь.

The works of our great thinkers play an important role in studying the history of the development of moral teachings of the peoples of Central Asia. In the Middle Ages, wise thinkers who put forward advanced moral ideas also appeared in other Eastern countries. Especially in the 9th-12th centuries, favorable historical, social and political conditions were created in Central Asia for the high development of culture, science and philosophy.[1] The theoretical heritage of Central Asian thinkers in the field of philosophy and ethics has become an important contribution to universal culture. The development of their philosophical views, as well as their attitude to the state, social life, and the development of moral and aesthetic views, was influenced by Islam. In the moral teachings of scholars, man is considered the greatest supreme being.

These thinkers determined the value of everything with humanity, and the ideas of humanism rose to a high level in the moral system. Al-Farabi deeply assimilated and propagated the philosophical views of Aristotle. For example, commenting on Aristotle's moral teachings, he

writes: “Everything that considers the highest happiness to be only in this world, and happiness to be outside this world, is foolishness”. [2] In his works “On the Attainment of Happiness”, “The City of Virtuous People” and others, Al-Farabi describes in detail the issues of social life, as well as the moral standards, relationships and rules of conduct of the people living in a virtuous city. Al-Farabi thinks from the point of view of eudaemonism in describing man and society.

He adheres to the principle of the interdependence of reason and morality. The philosopher connects moral standards with intelligence. In his opinion, an intelligent person is perfect in all respects, including morally. When a person strives for perfection, he must also strive for intellectual knowledge. Only then will he achieve his noble intention, that is, happiness. In order to have good virtue, a person must embody all positive qualities in himself. In particular, a person should be physically, morally, and mentally perfect, that is, he should be intelligent, intelligent, knowledgeable, well-mannered, pure, just, humane, generous, firm in his actions and thoughts, courageous, and devoid of fear and weakness. [3] All of this is achieved through knowledge. Al-Farabi divides human virtues into two, namely theoretical virtues and practical artistic (vocational) virtues.

A person achieves happiness with the help of these virtues. According to Al-Farabi, wisdom is a virtue that provides knowledge about happiness, and prudence is a virtue that provides knowledge about achieving happiness. Al-Farabi also thinks about virtue and emphasizes that it is formed due to the kindness that arises from being involved in goodness. [4] These thoughts are of great importance for our country, which has gained its independence and is developing boldly towards the future. If each person cannot predict and imagine his future in the form of a great goal, his creative activity will weaken and gradually begin to lose its shape.

According to Al-Farabi, the goal of human existence is to achieve the highest happiness, first of all, one must know what this happiness is and what it consists of, make achieving it an idea and the highest goal for oneself, and be fascinated with it with all one's being. Then one must personally begin to do the things that will lead to this happiness. Therefore, in order to achieve happiness, a person must be active and proactive. According to Al-Farabi, happiness is achieved through knowledge and enlightenment, because it is important for acquiring complete and perfect knowledge of the essence and content of the world, as well as for acquiring a profession. Al-Farabi shows that education is extremely necessary for a person to achieve perfection. He pays attention to consciousness and morality in a person's spiritual life. Al-Farabi believes that human morality as a whole is a criterion for determining his activity, that is, the spiritual wealth and content of a person are manifested in his moral actions. [5] In his treatise “On the Achievement of Happiness”, Al-Farabi emphasizes that in order for a person to effectively perceive beauty, he must have a subtle nature and a foundation of intellectual perfection, and only a person with emotional and intellectual abilities can know all the secrets of the world. He argues that a person becomes a true person due to his intelligence, knowledge brings happiness and joy to a person, and through knowledge a person discovers beauty and perfection in himself. Al-Farabi encourages people to engage in science and art, and shows that thanks to this, beautiful things become understandable. Al-Farabi emphasizes the role of poetry and music in the self-education of a person and his aesthetic development. In his opinion, all types of art are different from each other: poetry works with words, and fine art with paints, but they have the same effect on a person. He emphasizes that, following Aristotle, both of these arts aim to influence the imagination and feelings of people through imitation. In the teachings of Beruni, the essence of morality is viewed in relation to the

way of life of people.[6] Beruni tries to explain the content of morality by linking it with social phenomena, the material needs and interests of people. In his opinion, a person, having a mind, as a possessor of the power of thought, is ordered to improve the country and establish order. Therefore, he promotes the ideas of patriotism in his works. In Beruni's moral teachings, truthfulness and justice are considered as concepts of equal value. Lying and evil turn a person away from justice, oppression, betrayal of trust cause the corruption of the people and are considered bad manners. A person, by educating his world, cleansing his soul of bad manners, and through moral treatment, reaches perfection and becomes free from negative manners.

Although the renewal of manners depends on the person himself, it is also determined by circumstances. Biruni believes that human happiness lies in knowledge and enlightenment. He praises the goodness of man and his noble moral qualities, while condemning the negative vices in man. He considers creative labor and goodness to be the basis for the meaning of life. Labor leaves a mark on life, and generations enjoy its fruits. At the same time, he condemns violence, forced labor, and honors free labor. Moral issues occupy a large place in Ibn Sina's creative work. The teacher gives a large place to these problems in his works "Morals", "Science of Morals", "Family Building" and others. His moral teachings stemmed from socio-political and philosophical ideas.

According to Ibn Sina, ethics is a science that distinguishes good from evil and provides conditions for a person to be happy. He includes good and evil, intelligence, pleasure, wisdom, generosity, love, humility, suffering, loyalty, aspiration, and others in the principles of morality. Human justice is the most important decoration of human behavior. In his opinion, justice is the main measure of spiritual pleasure. Justice appears with the three desires of a person: patience, courage, and wisdom. If a person has this virtue, he can protect himself, strengthen goodness in himself, and achieve true spiritual pleasure. Therefore, justice is the criterion of good and evil. Ibn Sina contrasts the good moral qualities of a person with the bad behavior and actions of people. He includes such bad qualities as deception, hatred, weakness, hostility, revenge, slander, and lack of will among the negative defects of a person.[7] The thinker emphasizes that one of the shortcomings of a person is ignorance, which is the opposite of work. In this way, he condemns selfishness and hypocrisy, calls to distinguish true friends from false ones. "A good friend," he says, "is a mirror that reflects all the good and bad qualities of a person. A good friend points out all the shortcomings in time, and helps to eliminate these shortcomings with his advice and behavior.

Honesty, loyalty, pure love, will, cunning, One of the thinkers who made a huge contribution to the development of moral teachings was Abu Ali ibn Sina. Ibn Sina's moral teachings are mainly set out in his works "Treatise on the Science of Morality", "Treatise on Duty", "Treatise on Keeping the Soul Pure", "Book on Justice", "Events in Residential Areas". 95 triumphs over evil, hypocrisy, and friendship only for one's own benefit is evil. One of the important aspects of Ibn Sina's moral teachings is the issue of children's education. He emphasizes the important role that education plays in the development of a person's moral qualities, and believes that the main goal of education is to instill good moral qualities in a child. In his opinion, the role of the community in moral education is great. Ibn Sina recognizes that educating the younger generation is an important task of the family and the state, the development of society, and the economic and cultural achievements of society directly depend on the growth of educated, cultured people, and teaches that "all things that have knowledge tend to perfection". In the term "perfection" he expresses a person's inner beauty and striving for goodness.

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